

TRADITIONAL KNOWLEDGE AND NATURAL REMEDIES AGAINST DERMATOSES IN UPPER GUINEA (REPUBLIC OF GUINEA)

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ABSTRACT

Skin diseases constitute a significant public health problem worldwide, particularly in tropical countries. The objective of this study was to assess the traditional knowledge of skin diseases held by traditional healers in Upper Guinea, as well as their traditional therapeutic practices for treating these diseases. To achieve this objective, an ethnobotanical survey was conducted with 41 individuals in Upper Guinea, including 13 women, using a semi-structured open interview technique. The results reveal that local populations possess a fairly clear understanding of skin diseases, but due to a lack of case studies, this traditional knowledge remains limited. During the interviews, traditional healers proposed 14 categories of skin diseases and several treatment methods. In total, 54 species of medicinal plants, belonging to 28 botanical families, were identified along with their uses. The most represented families are Caesalpiniaceae (8 species), Apocynaceae (5 species), followed by Euphorbiaceae (4 species), Moraceae (4 species),

and Meliaceae (3 species). Leaves are the most commonly used part of the plant, followed by bark and roots. The most prevalent method of preparing remedies is decoction, followed by

powder. and maceration. The primary method of acquiring these recipes remains learning. The literature reveals that several of the plants mentioned are rich in bioactive compounds likely to effectively combat dermatoses.

KEYWORDS: Dermatoses, traditional knowledge, medicinal plants.

INTRODUCTION

Plants have always been used as medicines throughout history. Herbal medicines are considered less toxic and gentler than pharmaceutical drugs. The pharmaceutical industry is increasingly interested in the ethnobotanical study of plants. Africa has a significant diversity of medicinal plants. These plants are valuable resources for the vast majority of rural populations in Africa, where more than 80% rely on them for healthcare (Jiofack et al., 2009; Jiofack et al., 2010; Dibong et al., 2011).

Plant species are very rich in terms of their number and diversity (Spichiger et al., 2000). In addition to their role in maintaining ecosystem balance, plants provide humans with essential natural resources for their survival and development. They are important for pharmacological research and drug development, not only when constituents are used directly as therapeutic agents, but also as raw materials for drug synthesis or as models for pharmacologically active compounds (Hadjadj et al., 2012).

Dermatoses are skin conditions caused by climatic, ecological, human, and social factors. The main conditions are: superficial fungal infections, bacterial dermatoses, parasitic dermatoses, and tropical skin ulcers (National Therapeutic Guide, 2013). A study conducted by Lando et al. (2004) at the Yaoundé hospital showed that dermatological conditions are frequent during infection with the human immunodeficiency virus (HIV). They also constitute a real public health problem worldwide and in tropical countries, where they account for 30% of consultations in rural areas. Little data is generally available on the epidemiology of these diseases in these countries (Basset et al., 1999; Clyti et al., 2006).

In Guinea, although common, dermatoses are very little studied, where the most recent work is that of Cissé (2006) carried out at the Donka University Hospital Center. In an effort to contribute to the appreciation of plants used in the treatment of dermatoses in traditional Guinean medicine, we conducted an ethnobotanical survey on the plants used in traditional Guinean medicine for the treatment of dermatoses in Upper Guinea. The objective of this

study is to identify some medicinal plants and the traditional therapeutic knowledge linked to their uses in the traditional management of dermatoses.

STUDY AREAS

Geographical Location

Upper Guinea, or the Upper Niger Basin, is one of the four natural regions of Guinea. It is a vast region located between 8° and 11°37' West longitude and between 8°45' and 12°35' North latitude. It covers an area of 103,235 km², representing approximately 41% of Guinea's territory. It is bordered to the west by Middle Guinea, to the north and east by Mali, and to the south by Côte d'Ivoire, Forest Guinea, Liberia, and part of Sierra Leone.

Upper Guinea owes its name to its location far from the coast and its altitude, corresponding to the eastern part of northern Guinea. Administratively, it is divided into two regions: the Kankan region, comprising the prefectures of Kankan, Siguiiri, Mandiana, Kouroussa and Kérouané, and the Faranah region, composed of the prefectures of Faranah, Dabola, and Dinguiraye (Beavogui, 2000).

Climate: Upper Guinea is under the influence of the South Sudanese (Sudanian-Guinean) tropical climate, characterized by the alternation of two seasons.

- a dry season from November to April with the predominance of easterly winds (harmattan)
- a rainy season from May to October with rainfall decreasing from south to north.

The average annual rainfall calculated over 30 years (1961-1990) varies from 1200 to 2400 mm from north to south.

Vegetation: Linked to the climate, the vegetation of Upper Guinea exhibits a marked north-south gradient. The open wooded savanna in the north contrasts with the tree-covered savanna in the south. Generally speaking, Upper Guinea is divided into three main vegetation zones.

- The Sudanese savanna lies in the far north. It is a sparsely wooded savanna. Occasionally, one finds a few rare patches of forest along the edges of the laterite hills. It covers the prefectures of Siguiiri and northern Mandiana.
- The humid savanna covers the entire central region, with some degraded highland forests in the prefectures of Dabola and Dinguiraye. In this part of Upper Guinea, the inter-river areas are covered with dense dry forests. To the south, particularly in the prefectures of

Kérouané, east of Faranah, south of Kankan, and west of Kouroussa, wooded savanna and secondary forests are found in sparsely populated areas.

- a forest-savanna mosaic: this is the forest-savanna transition zone which is in contact with the Sudanese-Guinean forests.

Herbaceous vegetation composed of tall grasses is also a characteristic of this region (Beavogui, 2000).

Population and demographic distribution

Upper Guinea has 2,645,453 inhabitants, representing 24.89% of the national population (RGPH3; 2014).

The population of Upper Guinea is homogeneous. It belongs primarily to the Mandé or Malinké ethnic group. The population is very unevenly distributed. The largest portion is concentrated in the valleys, towns, and mining areas. Non-Malinké settlements persist on the peripheries (Beavogui, 2000).

Figure 1: Presentation of study areas in Upper Guinea.

ETHNOBOTANICAL SURVEY METHOD

The interview is the research technique used. It consists of a one-on-one oral exchange between two people, one of whom provides information to the other. The procedure adopted is the semi-structured interview, where the interviewee is invited to answer the interviewer's questions comprehensively, in their own words and using their own frame of reference. A questionnaire was developed for this purpose, and the questions were asked in the interviewee's language.

The information is transcribed onto standardized forms and validated by the Institute for Research and Development of Medicinal and Food Plants of Guinea (IRDPMAG)-Dubreka.. The study focused on communities in Upper Guinea and the medicinal plants from the wild flora that they use to treat skin conditions. The sampling was random. A total of 41 traditional healers were surveyed. The survey was conducted in the prefectures of Kankan, Kouroussa, Siguri, Mandiana, and Kérouané.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PEOPLE SURVEYED

In Upper Guinea, and particularly in the Kankan administrative region, we surveyed 41 people, including 13 women. In general, the people surveyed have the following characteristics.

The age range varies between 20 and 90 years with a predominance in the 45-55 age group, i.e. 17 people for a percentage of 41.46. Twenty-four people reported receiving their healing practices through apprenticeship (58.54%), and thirteen people (31.71%) received their practices from a family member. Only two people learned the art of healing through personal experience. One person began practicing healing after recovering from an illness, and another received their practice from their community.

In this region of Guinea, all socio-professional categories are interested in traditional medicine. During our survey, we interviewed 25 registered healers, representing 60.97% of the total, and 11 herbalists, representing 26.83% of the total, including nine women. This could be explained by the fact that in Upper Guinea, women generally perform light work, which makes it easier for them to practice this profession. In addition, it provides them with daily income. We also interviewed two hunters, two fetish priests, and one farmer.

In summary, based on these results, we can say that traditional medicine remains the primary healthcare option in Upper Guinea, with younger people (45 to 55 years old) being the most represented group. The primary method of acquiring these remedies remains learning.

TRADITIONAL CONSIDERATIONS ON DERMATOSES

According to our sources, there are several types of dermatoses.

In Upper Guinea, skin diseases are called "fadi kan dyankarolu," which literally means skin diseases. These diseases are well known and treated by the local population; they are numerous and varied. They include.

"Sorinyan"

Scabies is known in traditional Guinean medicine as "sorinyan", which literally means "nail amuse." Any skin condition that itches intensely and causes scratching lesions is given this name. According to our informants in the cities of Kankan and Siguiri, "sorinyan" is the scabies of dirty people. It smells very bad and can contaminate everyone around it. The pathogen of human scabies is *Sarcoptes scabiei* var. *hominis* (Bruno, 2020). The forms encountered according to traditional Guinean medicine are as follows.

- "Gboya"

This type of scabies is considered to be the result of fetish poisoning; a magical manipulation performed by someone. It produces bumps, and when scratched, these bumps become darker than the surrounding skin. The resulting dark patches multiply and eventually cover the entire body. This skin inflammation could be scientifically explained by post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation, the scratching of which aggravates the inflammation and stimulates the production of melanin (skin pigment).

- "Kaliya Bunbun"

This refers to an itching that occurs after contact with certain plants or animals (during corn or rice harvests, in chicken coops, etc.). The body suddenly becomes covered in large bumps that can completely cover the body and merge together. In addition to the itching, the patient suffers from headaches and a burning sensation. Shortly after taking the remedy, the bumps and discomfort disappear suddenly without leaving a trace. This is allergic or irritant contact dermatitis (Gambillara *et al.*, 2010).

"Wagna"

The most contagious forms of scabies are called "Wagna" in Malinké, which evokes the idea of itching. These are other forms of scabies according to traditional Guinean medicine. Several forms are distinguished, including.

- "Wagna fin"

These are profuse scabies and hyperkeratotic scabies, which is taking on epidemic proportions. **It is called "Wagna fin" in Malinke** and evokes the idea of something turning black. It is characterized by intense itching and the formation of black spots and scratch lesions. The high contagiousness observed in this type of scabies is explained by the fact that the parasite density is much higher in this case, unlike classic scabies where the parasite load is about ten female mites living on the skin (Bruno, 2020).

- "Kènèkan wagna"

"Kènèkan wagna" in Malinke, is also incorrectly classified in Guinean Traditional Medicine as a type of scabies. In fact, this itching is due to infestation by pubic lice, also called "morpions" in French and "kènèsilagnamoun" in Malinke, which are different from mites, the parasites responsible for scabies.

- "Wagnadjima"

It's a skin allergy which would be caused by insects called "Samakoro and dabi" in Malinke, that is to say, bedbugs **It is called "Wagnadjima," meaning "hydrated scabies."** It manifests as a rash of bumps on the points where the insect bites. These bumps absorb water and burst when scratched. It is highly contagious because bumps will form wherever this fluid comes into contact with the skin.

It should also be noted that in traditional Guinean medicine, there is another form of scabies attributed to witchcraft called "Soubagnaman." It is believed to be linked to a curse cast by sorcerers. It is very complicated because it is difficult to treat and manifests itself in all forms of scabies.

"Kuna"

Known as "Kuna" in Malinke, leprosy is a greatly feared disease also called "Dyankaroba," meaning "great disease." It is characterized by the appearance of white or red patches on the skin, which loses all sensation, even when pinched with fingernails. This description of the

disease is consistent with that of Berche (2019), who states that the disease begins with depigmented skin patches predominantly on the face, often accompanied by a loss of skin sensation and inflammatory hypertrophy of the major nerve trunks, leading to paralysis. It is an infectious, transmissible disease caused by *Mycobacterium leprae*, or Hansen's bacillus (1873), which particularly affects the skin, mucous membranes, peripheral nervous system, and eyes (Aubry and Gaüzère, 2024).

“Nyaman”

All skin conditions characterized by non-generalized bumps that manifest as itchy spots or smooth, non-itchy patches are known as "Nyaman" in Malinke. Nyaman could refer to hives, eczema, or skin allergies. Unlike "kuna," meaning leprosy, the spots here are sensitive to pinching. The most well-known forms are.

- **“Bala nyaman”**

These are skin infections characterized by the presence of pimples that burst, releasing a compacted pus which, upon contact with air, forms a white crust under the hair and on the rest of the child's body. This refers to childhood skin infections such as folliculitis, boils, or impetigo.

- **“Sa nyaman” or “fubayi nyaman”** (sâ = snake)

This type of skin infection is characterized by the appearance of smooth, colored patches on the skin that resemble "viper skin." The disease is named after a highly venomous snake (fubayi) whose skin has the same mosaic pattern as that of a viper. The early stages of leprosy are often confused with this condition. However, in the case of “foubayi nyaman”, the patches retain their sensitivity. This pathology is highly contagious and affects the entire body. The description given could refer to ringworm (*tinea corporis*).

- **“Tödi nyaman”**

When the sores burst and release a clear fluid, it is called "tödi nyaman." The disease takes its name from the toad (“Tödi”) whose skin secretes a liquid when it is disturbed. Based on the symptoms described, this infection resembles an abscess or a boil.

- **“Bo nyaman”**

According to traditional healers in Siguiiri and Kankan, Guinea, this disease is caused by dirty water and is common among bare feet during the rainy season. It is located between the toes

or fingers and manifests as intense itching. Scratching causes sores. This is almost certainly athlete's foot, also known as tinea pedis, caused by dermatophytes (Taurinya, 2020).

- **“Tolola nyaman”** (Tolo = ear)

This condition is most commonly seen in children, affecting the ears. It is otitis, a viral or bacterial infection behind the eardrum.

- **“nyaman fing”** (Fing = blackened)

It is caused by small worms that live in the water. It is characterized by an eruption of small bumps on the skin as a result of scratching; the skin becomes very dark and heavy (thick). This is known as swimmer's itch or "cercariasis," caused by cercariae, the larvae of aquatic parasites that live in fresh water.

“Bassa gbolo” (meaning lizard skin)

It causes scaly patches in places on the skin, which are whitish in color. These areas often become hard and ridged. The symptoms presented could be mistaken for pityriasis versicolor, tinea versicolor (dry skin), or vitiligo.

“Têde-sêgna”

It manifests as a lump that forms on the sole of the foot; this is a plantar fibroma.

“Wara-wara” (color mixture)

This infection manifests as the appearance of superficial whitish spots on the body. It is more common in people with poor personal hygiene. When these spots are scratched, they cause the skin to flake. This condition is not very serious, but it does discolor the skin, giving it various hues. This infection is scientifically known as pityriasis versicolor, a benign fungal infection caused by a fungus (*Malassezia*).

“Makuru”

It consists of bumps in the creases of babies' joints. These bumps burst and lead to sores that can merge if the infection is not stopped. This could correspond to infectious skin lesions such as boils, abscesses, or bullous impetigo.

“Bombönin and Mayon”

These skin conditions are characterized by itching and burning sensations followed by thickening of the skin and the appearance of small bumps, giving it a rough texture. The skin tends to tear. The symptoms described correspond to those of eczema.

"Sumunin (boil)"

A small, painful, pointed bump that eventually grows to the size of a cola nut before naturally oozing pus. This is a boil, a bacterial skin infection that develops around a hair follicle, usually caused by the *Staphylococcus aureus* bacterium.

“Kotè”

It is a skin infection that manifests as sores between the buttocks and even in the mouth of babies. It is probably a contagious viral infection called Hand, Foot and Mouth Disease (HFMD) or diaper rash and thrush (oral candidiasis), which is most common in young children.

"Kolo" (kolo means bone)

A small, stubborn swelling, resistant to conventional treatments, with minimal elevation and radiating pain to other parts of the body. Appropriate treatment allows for the extraction from the patient's body of a short, hard, straight, white, worm-like object, resembling a bone, from which the disease derives its name (kolo means bone). Some treatments can "kill" this "worm" within the body. Then the abscess heals without suppurating (another translation of its name, related to the mode of transmission through long-distance spells). Some traditional healers do not hesitate to infect numerous people and then offer their services for a fee. This skin infection is scientifically known as a parasitic abscess, which can be caused either by fly larvae (furuncular myiasis) or other parasites such as the sand flea (tungiasis).

“Nörö”

This condition has long been known in traditional Mandinka medicine as a stubborn disease contracted through sexual intercourse. It was once very rare. Two forms are distinguished: an acute form and a chronic form. The chronic patient loses considerable weight, may or may not cough, and numerous other stubborn illnesses complicate their clinical picture: influenza, malaria, itching, diarrhea, etc. The individual very often ends up succumbing to tuberculosis resistant to known treatments for this disease. This is why chronic nörö has been considered a

very serious form of tuberculosis. As described, it is undoubtedly a sexually transmitted infection.

"Kaba"

Kaba refers to dermatoses that cause hair loss in a specific area of the body, leaving a characteristic rough texture. The term kaba, without further qualification, refers to tinea capitis, dandruff, and rough skin conditions that begin as small, patchy lesions on other parts of the body. There are several types, including.

- "kaba fin" = black moth, which looks like coal kneaded in water.
- "Kaba wulen" or "kaba wuleman" = red ringworm, which is characterized by red spots on the skin. At first, it resembles leprosy (djankaroba), and if left untreated, it develops into leprosy.
- "kaba gbèman" = white ringworm, which manifests itself by the appearance of small white bumps on the head and causes hair to fall out.

Table 2: Classification of dermatological conditions in the local Malinke language and their traditional treatment.

Pathology	Traditional name	Cause	Demonstration	Treatment
Scabies	Sorinyan	Lack of hygiene	Itching and the appearance of lesions after scratching	The decoction of the leaves of <i>Piper umbellatum</i> L. (Pèmènènaa (K)) in body bath.
	Gboya	A curse originating from a fetish	Appearance of pimples that turn black after scratching and spread all over the body	The decoction of the leafy lianas of <i>Cissus populnea</i> Guill. & Perr. (Bumban) in body bath .
	Kaliya Bunbun	Contact with certain plants or animals (during corn or rice harvests, in chicken coops, etc.)	Large spots that can completely cover the body, itching, headaches , fever.	A decoction of the roots and stem bark of <i>Fagara zanthoxyloides</i> L (wô) in a body bath ;
Leprosy	Kuna or Dyankaroba	Insect bites and bites from other smaller organisms in the water.	Appearance of white or red spots on the skin, which loses all sensation . Loss of toes and fingers.	Root of <i>Vitex doniana</i> (Kodoba) + bark or decocted leaves, roots of <i>Diospyros mespiliformis</i> (Dabakala sunsun) + root of <i>Guiera senegalensis</i> (karangbelen) + leaves of <i>Ficus exasperata</i> (Kotorolen) or <i>Cassia nigricans</i> L. (Limönin na tali) + slice of lemon, used in a body bath.
Parasitosis	Nyaman	Poor hygiene,	Non-generalized	The decoction of the leaves and

		unprotected sex.	pimples accompanied by itching or by smooth spots that do not itch.	roots of <i>Uvaria chamae</i> P. Beauv. (Shivers); of the bark of <i>Combretum fragrans</i> F. Hoffm (Samabalin); of the bark of <i>Margaritaria discoidea</i> (Baill.) Webster (Bâkônkôn); of the leaves of discoid <i>Phyllanthus</i> Mull. Arg. (Surukugnegne); of the barks and roots of <i>Tamarindus indica</i> L. (Fallen); of the leaves of <i>Nauclea pobeguini</i> (Pob.Pellegr) Petit (Kobadi); The decoction of the leaves of <i>Piper umbellatum</i> L. (First); decoction of the bark of <i>Ficus ingens</i> Miq. (Soutoro); the decoction of the leaves of <i>T richilia roka</i> (Forsk.) Chior. (Soulafinsan); the decoction of the whole plant of <i>Leucas martinicensis</i> (Jacq.) R.Br. (Dasidâadala or Dassidadala); the decoction of the leaves of <i>Psorospermum guinea</i> Spach . (Carignakouma); the decoction of the leaves of <i>Erythrina senegalensis</i> DC (Yerun) in body bath.
	Bala nyaman	Contact with certain caterpillars that leave their hairs on the skin. Lack of hygiene.	Presence of pimples that burst to release a compact pus	Apply the powder from the leaves of " Gbanin ", " Kurangbayi ", " dafin sagba » after a bath with the decoction of the aforementioned leaves;
	Sa nyaman ou fubayi nyaman	Caused by small debris in the wind. Lack of hygiene.	Presence of leprosy-like spots all over the body, but tender; highly contagious disease	Bark or seed of <i>Khaya senegalensis</i> (Diala) reduced to powder and applied locally. Decoction of the roots of <i>Entada africana</i> (Dialakamban) or leaves of <i>Combretum Molle</i> (Wanyaka) to drink and bathe.
	Tödi nyaman	Contact with toxic fungi. Lack of hygiene.	The appearance of pimples that burst to release a clear liquid	The decoction and oil of the bark and fruit of <i>Carapa procera</i> DC (Kobi) in body baths and local application ; the consumption and localized application of the powder or paste of the leaves of <i>Cassia nigricans</i> L. (Limönin na tali);
	Bo nyaman	Disease caused by contact of the feet with dirty, infected water, particularly during the rainy season.	Severe itching leading to a sore after scratching	Body bath with the decoction of the leaves of <i>Crossopteryx febrifugea</i> (Afzel. ex G. Don) Benth. (Kinyènkinyèn or Kienké) or with the maceration of the barks of <i>Colas cordifolia</i> (Cav.) R. Br.

				(Tabaa) associated with the barks of <i>Saba senegalensis</i> (ADC) Pichon (Sagba).
	Tolola nyaman	Dust + water. Humidity	A sore appearing on the ears of children in particular	Wash the wound with the decoction of the stem bark of <i>Carapa procera</i> DC (Kobi) or apply the crushed leaves + tuber of <i>Calotropis procera</i> (Baadjuba).
	nyaman fing	Contact with small worms in the water	eruption of small bumps on the skin as a result of scratching	The decoction of the roots of <i>Landolphia dulcis</i> (R.Br.Ex Sabine) Small (Ködoudou); roots, shells and barks of <i>Adansonia digitata</i> L. (Silk); of leafy liane of <i>Cissus populnea</i> Guill. & Perr. (Boumban); decoction and sap of the bark of <i>Ficus dicranostyla</i> Mildbr. (Select) body bath and topical application.
pityriasis versicolor (Mycose)	Bass leather	Contact with certain insects.	Appearance of scaly patches in places on the skin, whitish in color	The decoction of the leafy stem of <i>Carissa edulis</i> Vahl (Souloukou Tömbörö); of the bark and roots of <i>Swartzia madagascariensis</i> (Engl.&K.) Dancer (Samakada); the decoction and powder of the leaves of <i>Cassia nigricans</i> L. (Limönin na tali) in a body bath.
Scabies of parasitic origin	Wagna	Dirt	Itching	The decoction, powder and ointment of the bark or root of <i>Fagara zanthoxyloides</i> L (wo); The combination of the bark or roots of <i>Fagara zanthoxyloides</i> L (wô) and <i>Securidaca longepedunculata</i> Fres. (djodo), pounded together with shea butter in body bath and local application.
	Wagna fin	Scabies of parasitic origin	Intense itching and the formation of black spots and scratching lesions.	The decoction, ash and powder of leaves and roots of <i>Opilia celtidifolia</i> (Guill. & Perr) Endl. (Kourangbei); the decoction and oil of the bark and fruit of <i>Carapa procera</i> DC (Kobi) for body baths and hydration. The decoction of the leaves of <i>Psorospermum guineense</i> Spach. (Karignakouma); the decoction of the bark of <i>Erythrophleum suaveolens</i> (Guil. & Per) Brenan. (Tali) for body baths.
	Kènèkan wagna	due to insects called "kènèsilagnamoun" (pubic lice)	It's pubic scabies.	The decoction of the leaves <i>Detarium microcarpum</i> Guill. & Perr. (Tambalén) in a body bath.

	Wagna djima	It is caused by insects " Samakoro and dabi = bedbug",	Rash following the insect bite; Susceptibility to secondary infection	The decoction of the barks and fruits of <i>Spondia mombin</i> L. (Ninkon); powder or decoction of leaves or roots of <i>Bridelia ferruginea</i> Benth. (Dâfinsagba) in body bath and local application.
	Soubagnaman	A spell cast by the wizards.	Manifests in all forms of scabies and is difficult to treat.	A decoction of the roots and stem bark of <i>Fagara zanthoxyloides</i> L (wô) in a body bath ;
Plantar fibroma	Têde-sêgna	Walking barefoot means frequent contact of the ground with bare feet.	Formation of a tumor that forms on the sole of the foot.	The sap or decoction of the leaves of <i>Jatropha curcas</i> L (Séguébâanin) in a body bath and local application.
Vitiligo (Fungal Infection)	Wara-wara	Lack of personal hygiene	Appearance of superficial whitish spots on the skin accompanied by scratching.	Burn the leaves of <i>Opilia celtidifolia</i> (Guill. & Perr) Endl. (Kurangbayi) , transform the ashes into potash for topical application
Impetigo	Makuru	Germes in the air.	Bumps in the creases of babies' joints that burst and cause sores.	Decoction of the leaves of <i>Bridelia ferruginea</i> Benth. (Dâfinsagba), <i>Alchornea cordifolia</i> (Koyiran), <i>Vernonia colorata</i> (Dakunan), <i>Combretum paniculatum</i> Vent. (Toubalanombö ladon) (drink and in body bath).
Atopic eczema	Bombonin and Mayon	Bad luck, witchcraft, STIs.	Itching and burning sensations followed by thickening of the skin which tends to tear and the appearance of small bumps giving a rough appearance.	a decoction of the rhizomes of <i>Anchomanes difformis</i> (Konban). Apply a paste or powder made from the tubers of <i>Dioscorea alata</i> (Gbaara). Apply crushed fresh fruits of <i>Hibiscus esculentus</i> (Gban). Apply flour made from <i>Pennisetum gambiense</i> (Sagnö) mixed with honey.
Boil	Sumunin	Humidity, allergens	A small, painful, pointed bump appears, which eventually grows to the size of a cola cotyledon before naturally suppurating.	Local application of <i>Citrus aurantifolia</i> Swingle fruit juice (Lemunum kumun);
Diaper rash and thrush (oral candidiasis)	Kotè	Vitamin deficiency, malnutrition.	Appearance of sores between the buttocks and even in the mouths of babies.	Give the child the fruit juice of <i>Adansonia digitata</i> L. (Seda). Wash the child with the decoction of the bark of <i>Bridelia ferruginea</i> Benth. (Dâfinsagba).
Parasitic abscess	Kolo	A kind of kotè (fetishes), a bad spell.	Appearance of small swelling resistant to	Decoction of the leaves + roots of <i>Ximenia americana</i> L (Sênê or

		Ingestion of the parasite through contaminated food.	usual treatments, causing pain in other parts of the body	Gbanin) associated with the leaves of <i>Prosopis africana</i> (Guill. et Perr.) Taub. (Gbélen) in bath and local application. Ground <i>Hibiscus esculentus</i> (Gban) or macerated <i>Erythrina senegalensis</i> DC (Yerun) in local application and bath.
Sexually transmitted infection	Nörö	Sleeping with other men's wives (bad luck). Sleeping with old women, parasites.	Two forms of manifestation: an acute form and a chronic form causing weight loss, coughing, and numerous stubborn illnesses.	The decoction of the leaves of <i>Alternanthera sessilis</i> Guil. & Perr. (Tentogola); the decoction of the leaves of <i>T richilia roka</i> (Forsk.) Chior. (Soulafinsan) in body bath.
Ringworm	Kaba	Poor hygiene (doesn't wash their hair)	Itchy, scaly growths on the head	The decoction of the fruits and leaves of <i>Saba senegalensis</i> (ADC) Pichon (Sagba); roots, shells and barks of <i>Adansonia digitata</i> L. (Séda); the sap or decoction of the leaves of <i>Jatropha curcas</i> L (Séguébâanin); the decoction and oil of the bark and fruit of <i>Carapa procera</i> DC (Kobi); the decoction of all parts of <i>Abutilon mauritanium</i> (Jack.) Medic. (Tolisiguikodon); the juice of the leaves of (kösafinet) applied locally;
	kaba fin	Caused by contact of certain worms in the dust.	Black mite	The decoction of the leafy stem of <i>Carissa edulis</i> Vahl (Souloukou Tömbörö); the decoction and ointment of the bark or roots of <i>Securidaca longepedunculata</i> Fres. (Djodo); the decoction of the leaves of <i>Psorospermum guineense</i> Spach. (Karignakouma); the decoction of the roots and stem bark of <i>Fagara zanthoxyloides</i> L « wô » in body bath;
	kaba wuleman or kaba wuleman	Due to a worm	Red spots on the skin	The decoction of the leaves and roots of <i>Landolphia heudelotii</i> ADC (Gbaï); the decoction and ointment of the bark or roots of <i>Securidaca longepedunculata</i> Fres. (Djodo); the decoction of the roots and stem bark of <i>Fagara zanthoxyloides</i> L « wô » in body bath;

ETHNOBOTANICAL INVESTIGATIONS ON PLANTS CITED FOR TREATING DERMATOSES IN UPPER GUINEA

Sampling was conducted on a voluntary basis among individuals recognized as possessing traditional knowledge within the community. Following surveys in Upper Guinea, 54 species of medicinal plants were cited by the respondents, belonging to 28 botanical families. Regarding preparation methods, we observed that the majority of traditional healers and herbalists interviewed stated that the plants can be harvested in the morning before the cool of the day. When collecting samples, some respondents indicated that the phrase "bissimilaye" should be pronounced while harvesting, and the samples should be dried within a day. If bark is to be collected from a tree, it is customary to harvest on the east and west sides of the tree. Decoction is the most common form of preparation, followed by powder, maceration, and infusion. Water is the most frequently used solvent. According to the healers interviewed, side effects are rarely observed; in general, these plants do not present toxic effects, which explains their use by generations for centuries.

Table 3: Plants cited for the treatment of dermatoses.

Vernacular name	Scientific name	Family	Parts used	Diseases treated
Tentogola (M)	Alternanthera sessilis Guil. & Perr.	AMARANTHACEAE	Leaves	Noro
			Leaves	Seguêbâ
Ninkon (M)	Spondia mombin L.	ANACARDIACEAE	Barks	IST
			Bark, Fruit	Wagna
Doloke (M)	Pseudospondia microcarpum (A. Rich.) Engl.	ANACARDIACEAE	Ecorces, Leaflets	Woyomba
Crying (M)	Uvaria chamae P. Beauv.	Annonaceae	Feuilles, Racines	Gnaman
Kanin (M)	Xylopia aethiopica (Dunal.) A. Rich.		Fruits	Korossinen, Aphrodisiaque
Ködoudou (M)	Landolphia dulcis (R.Br.Ex Sabine) Pichon	APOCYNACEAE	Racines	Yéguéré, Gnamafin
Kesagba (M)	Holarrhena floribunda (G.Dor.)Dur.& Schinz		Feuilles, Racines	Körösinen
Sagba (M)	Saba senegalensis (ADC) Pichon		Leaves	Soumaya
			Fruits, Leaves	News
Souloukou Tömbörö (M)	Carissa edulis Vahl		Leafy stems	Kabafin, Bassagbolo
Destroy (M)	Landolphia heudelotii ADC		Feuilles, Racine	Oil end
Digger (M)	Pachycarpus lineolatus	ASCLEPIADACEAE	Hair	Draw

	(Decne) Bullock			
Silk (M)	<i>Adansonia digitata</i> L.	BOMBACACEAE	Ecorces Racines, Coques de fruits	Gnaman Gnaman fin, Kaba
Tombé (M)	<i>Tamarindus indica</i> L.	CAESALPINIACEAE	Ecorces, Racines	Gnaman
Samakada (M)	<i>Swartzia madagascariensis</i> (Engl.&K.) Dancer		Ecorces	Palu chronique
Tambalén (M)	<i>Detarium microcarpum</i> Guill. & Perr.		Ecorces, Racine	Bassagbolo
Limönin na tali (M)	<i>Cassia nigricans</i> L.		Leaves	Palu, Kénékan Wagna,
Such (M)	<i>Erythrophleum suavedens</i> (Guil. & Per) Been.		Leaves	Bassagbolo, todi nyaman
Kötambalen (M)	<i>Cassia podocarpa</i> Guill. & Perr.		Ecorce,	Wagnafing
Sindja (M)	<i>Cassia sieberiana</i> A.D.		Leaves	Teigne
Tamba (M)	<i>Detarium macrocarpum</i> Guill.& Perr.		Young leaves	Teigne
Samabalin (M)	<i>Combretum fragrans</i> F. Hoffm.	COMBRETACEAE	Ecorce,	Dembalén, Sêgue
Total number of participants (M)	<i>Combretum paniculatum</i> Vent.			Draw
Bakonkon (M)	<i>Daisy discoidea</i> (Baill.) Webster	EUPHORBIACEAE	Ecorces	Ready
Surukugnege (M)	<i>Phyllanthus discoides</i> Mull. Arg.		Leaves	Gnaman, Dembalén
Dâfinsagba (M)	<i>Bridelia ferruginea</i> Benth.		Leaves, Roots	Wagnajima
Séguébâanin (M)	<i>Jatropha curcas</i> L.		Séve, Feuilles	Kaba, tédê
Yerun (M)	<i>Erythrina senegalensis</i> DC	FABACEAE	Leaves	Gnaman
Karignakouma (M)	<i>Psorospermum guineense</i> Spach.	HYPERICACEAE	Leaves	Gnaman, Kabafing
Soukouran (M)	<i>Ocimum gratissimum</i> L.	LABIACEAE	Leaves	Teigne
Dasidâadala ou Dassi dadala (M)	<i>Leucas martinicensis</i> (Jacq.) R.Br.	LAMIACEAE	Plante entière	Gnaman
Tolisiguikodon (M)	<i>Abutilon mauritianum</i> (Jack.) Medic.	MALVACEAE	Toutes les parties	Kaba
Soulafinsan (M)	<i>Trichilia roka</i> (Forsk.) Chior.	MELIACEAE	Leaves	Nörö, Gnaman, Palu chronique
Djala (M)	<i>Khaya senegalensis</i>		Ecorces	Gnamafing

	(Desr.) A. Juss.			
Kobi (M)	<i>Carapa procera</i> DC		Ecorce, Oil	Kaba, Wagnafing, Toligbolo
Gbélén (M)	<i>Prosopis africana</i> (Guill. et Perr.) Taub.	MIMOSACEAE	Leaves	Draw
Nere (M)	<i>Parkia biglobosa</i> (Jacq.) Benth.		Leaves	Draw
Djalo (Konia) or Waniaka (M)	<i>Ficus exasperata</i> Vahl	MORACEAE	Leaves	Teigne and Wales
Soutoro (M)	<i>Ficus engens</i> Miq.		Ecorces	Ready
Serial (M)	<i>Ficus glumosa</i> Del.		Hair, Leaves	Summer
Select (M)	<i>Ficus dicranostyla</i> Mildbr.		Ecorce, Seve	Gnamafing
Name (M)	<i>Musa paradisiaca</i> L.	MUSACEAE	Donzo (M)	Saupice (M), cabbage
			Banana Peel	Draw
Movie (M)	<i>Ximenia americana</i> L.	OLACACEAE	Roots	Wagnafing, Kaba
Kourangbei (M)	<i>Opilia celtidifolia</i> (Guill. & Perr) Endl.	OPIACEAE	Leaves, Roots	already, Sorignan Soubagnaman,
Böö (M)	<i>Oxythenanthera abyssinica</i> Munro.	POACEAE	Leaves	Körösinen, kaba fima
Kaba ou Gnö (M)	<i>Zea mays</i> L.		Foudou	Kaba wulén et fima
Djodo (M)	<i>Securidaca longedunculata</i> Fres.	POLYGALACEAE	Ecorces, Racines	Syphilis, Soumbagnaman, Bassagbolo
Kobadi (M)	<i>Nauclea pobeguini</i> (Pob.Pellegr) Petit	RUBIACEAE	Leaves	Gnaman
Kinyèn kinyèn ou Kienké (M)	<i>Crossopteryx febrifugea</i> (Afzel. ex G. Don) Benth.		Ecorce de tige	Teigne
Lémunum kumun (M)	<i>Citrus aurantifolia</i> Swingle	RUTTACEAE	Fruits	Furoncle
Wô (M)	<i>Fagara zanthoxyloides</i> L.		Ecorce ou racines	Wagna, teigne
Donsola dyanba (M)	<i>Allophulus africanus</i> P. Beauv.	SAPINDACEAE	Leaves	Teigne
Shea (F), Self (M)	<i>Vitellaria paradoxa</i> Gaerth.	SAPOTACEAE	Fruit, Oil or Butter	Draw
Tobacco (M)	<i>Colas cordifolia</i> (Cav.) R. Br.	STERCULIACEAE	Leaves, Barks	Draw
Boumban (M)	<i>Cissus populanea</i> Guill. & Perr.	VITACEAE	Leafy Lianas	Gnamafing, Gboya

Legend: (M) = Maninka ; (F) = French

In this table, we note that the most represented families are: Caesalpiniaceae (8 species), Apocynaceae (5 species), followed by Euphorbiaceae (4 species), Moraceae (4 species), and Meliaceae (3). Next, Anacardiaceae is represented by only two (2) species, Annonaceae (2) species, Combretaceae (2) species, Mimosaceae (2) species, Poaceae (2) species, Rubiaceae (2) species, and Ruttaceae (2) species. Finally, the other families are represented by only one species each, namely: Amaranthaceae, Asclepiadaceae, Bombacaceae, Fabaceae, Hypericaceae, Lamiaceae, Lamiaceae, Malvaceae, Musaceae, Olacaceae, Opiliaceae, Polygalaceae, Sapindaceae, Sapotaceae, Sterculiaceae, and Vitaceae.

A review of the literature shows that the most frequently cited plants are rich in bioactive compounds that can effectively combat dermatoses.

Studies have shown the potential of *Alternanthera sessilis* leaves for treating various skin problems, such as wounds, ulcers, rashes, and infections. This could be due to the fact that these leaves are rich in phytoconstituents such as flavonoids, phenols, and antioxidants, which confer antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and healing properties. Thus, they appear as a promising natural remedy for skin conditions (Kabeerdass et al., 2022).

Similarly, the roots and other parts of *Spondias mombin* L. are widely used in traditional medicine to treat various ailments, including skin conditions such as eczema, ringworm, wounds, and inflammation, due to their antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant properties, often attributed to compounds such as flavonoids and phenolic acids. Root/root bark extracts show potential for treating skin infections and reducing inflammation, supporting its traditional use, although further scientific validation is underway for specific applications of the root against skin diseases. (Maria et al., 2022).

According to Shehu et al. (2018), the bark and roots of *Pseudospondias microcarpa* have been traditionally used to treat skin conditions. Studies have shown that its extracts have significant antibacterial activity against bacteria such as *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, two important skin pathogens, suggesting its potential in treating infections due to its phenolic compounds. Research confirms that extracts of this plant possess analgesic and anti-inflammatory properties, reinforcing its traditional use for various conditions, including skin diseases, by reducing inflammation and fighting microbes, although further research is needed to identify specific active compounds and optimize topical applications.

The leaves and roots of *Uvaria chamae* are traditionally used and scientifically recognized for their ability to combat skin problems due to their potent antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory compounds (chalcones, polyphenols). They effectively fight bacteria such as *Staphylococcus aureus* and fungi, promote wound healing, and offer promising prospects for new treatments for skin infections in the form of creams and poultices, although there are risks associated with their topical application (Togbé *et al.*, 2024).

The leaves and roots of *Xylopia aethiopica* (Ethiopian pepper) are traditionally used and scientifically recognized for their potent antibacterial and antimicrobial properties in treating skin conditions. Extracts of these plants are effective against common skin pathogens such as *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, confirming their traditional use in treating wounds, boils, and infections. Preparations such as ointments and creams made from these extracts exhibit good skin compatibility, further supporting their role in the treatment of skin diseases (Fleischer *et al.*, 2008).

Leaves and roots *Landolphia heudelotii* (related to *L. owariensis*), a plant from West Africa, are traditionally used for their anti-infective and anti-inflammatory properties, and to treat skin conditions thanks to compounds such as betulinic acid. This suggests potential for treating skin diseases by fighting microbes and reducing inflammation. While research confirms its pharmacological potential (antimicrobial, antioxidant), more documentation on its specific cutaneous applications and active compounds for skin diseases is needed, but its traditional use for wounds and infections suggests its efficacy (Oladeji *et al.*, 2024).

The leaves and roots of *Securidaca longipedunculata* (purple tree) are traditionally used in African medicine to treat various conditions, including skin infections, due to their richness in phytochemical compounds such as flavonoids and saponins, which possess potent antibacterial, antifungal, anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties, making it a promising natural remedy for skin conditions and other infectious diseases (Ajali, and Chukwurah, 2004).

The bark and roots of *Saba senegalensis* are traditionally used in West African medicine to treat various ailments. Their extracts show promise for wound healing and skin problems due to their anti-inflammatory/antiseptic compounds, although specific studies on the bark/roots for skin diseases are less detailed than those on the leaves/fruit, which have revealed active compounds such as tannins, flavonoids, and terpenoids with potential

antimicrobial/antioxidant effects. Extracts of the plant, particularly the leaves and roots, are used in decoctions/poultices for burns, wounds, and general skin health, supporting ongoing scientific research into its dermatological applications (Dang-i et al., 2024).

The bark and roots of *Cassia nigricans* (often associated with *Senna* species such as *C. alata*) are traditionally used to treat skin conditions such as ringworm, eczema, and wound infections due to their antimicrobial, antifungal, and anti-inflammatory properties. Their extracts contain compounds such as flavonoids and tannins that act against bacteria and fungi, thus supporting their traditional use in treating various skin conditions and infections (Osunga et al., 2023).

CONCLUSION

This study showed that fifty-four (54) plant species are used to treat skin diseases by communities in Upper Guinea. Among the plant parts used, leaves are clearly predominant. Preparation methods are varied, but decoction is the most common. The traditional remedies are primarily administered topically. The traditional remedies identified in this study are of real interest for therapeutic management in rural areas. Indeed, it emerged that traditional healers have a thorough knowledge of skin diseases and the medicinal plants prescribed to treat them. During our interviews, the respondents suggested 14 categories of skin diseases and several treatment methods. This study is also being conducted with a view to implementing innovative initiatives that could lead to the future production of traditional medicines for the treatment of skin diseases in Guinea. It is therefore desirable to expand this inventory and identify effective plants for further analysis.

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